

Adamite, austinite, schlegelite, dugganite and other uncommon minerals in the “Cogolla Alta” claim, Belalcázar, Córdoba, Spain.

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Introduction

The “Cogolla Alta” claim (n° 10881) is part of a group of claims located in the “Santa Eufemia pluton”, a body of porphyritic monzogranites located about 3 km to the W of this town, embedded in shales and grawackas of Culm facies, from the upper Viséense - Namurian (Lower Carboniferous).

This pluton has an elliptical shape, with the major axis of about 12 km in length, in the EW direction, and the smallest, about 6 km, in the NS direction.

It is formed mainly by porphyritic monzogranites with potassium feldspar megacrystals of a size of up to 5 cm, with some leucogranite masses and dikes. Both types of rock contain cordierite, altered to pinnite (García Casco et al., 1989). In its periphery, embedded in the granites, but sometimes also in the slates of the area of contact metamorphism, are around a dozen of mineralizations with wolframite in quartz veins. In the zone of the old works of the “Cogolla Alta” mine, the granite is degraded in the surface, so that only the quartz veins stand out from the ground.

In the “Cogolla Alta” claim, two types of mineralization have been observed. One of them, located about 700 meters E of the Casa de Cogolla Alta, is formed by wolframite with barite, a very rare association known only in a few sites (Rechenberg, 1954). In addition to these minerals and the quartz veins, small amounts of conicalcite have been found.

Situation of the Cogolla Alta mine.

Geological map of the mineralizations in the region. In orange: Santa Eufemia pluton. In red: quartz veins.

The most interesting deposit from a mineralogical point of view, in which the paragenesis that will be described next appears, is located about 700 meters to the W of the previous ones. Some 300 meters to the SE of the buildings of the Cortijo de La Ventosilla and 500 meters to the W of the Casa de Cogolla Alta, also called Cortijo del Ventoso, building that is next to the Cogollarta geodesic vertex, about 9 km to the ESE of Belalcázar. Its geographic coordinates are 38 ° 33 '20.17' N and 5 ° 03 '38.55' W. The mining works consist of a trench of about 6 m in length following the quartz vein in the E-W direction. This trench is currently clogged with debris and garbage. There is also a small tailing that has been dispersed over the cultivated land and used to repair nearby trails.

The works of the “Alcantarilla” (or “Nuestra Señora de la Alcantarilla”) mine, where a large series of rare minerals such as karibibite have been found, some with a certain abundance, are located 1.5 km N of this deposit (Rewitzer *et al.*, 2016).

Minerals from the “Cogolla Alta” mine

Despite its proximity to the “Alcantarilla” mine, the “Cogolla Alta” mineralogy is substantially different. Arsenides are much scarcer in the primary mineralization, with only arsenopyrite appearing in very small quantities. The most frequent secondary mineral formed by its direct alteration, scorodite, is quite scarce. On the other hand, cobalt appears in the form of various secondary minerals and not forming differentiated primary minerals. Apparently, it is found inside quite altered arsenopyrite but of which there are still relicts. The presence of a tellurium mineral of secondary formation, as well as that of native gold, suggests the presence in the primary mineralization of some gold telluride, which has not been found so far. Another differential feature is the presence of scheelite, relatively common in the “Cogolla Alta” mine in crystal form, while in the “Alcantarilla” mine it is quite scarce. There are also zinc minerals, both primary and secondary, of which there are still relicts.

Search of minerals in the remains of the dump from the Cogolla Alta mine with abundant pieces of philonion quartz. Photo Norbert Röschl.

The most interesting secondary mineralization is found in small geodes within the quartz vein, where mineral microcrystals are deposited over small, colorless quartz crystals. Since the elements that constitute them can come from the mobilization of the alteration of different minerals of the primary paragenesis, the result is quite complex, including rare minerals. The direct alteration of the elements and sulfides present produces the formation of compact aureoles of other secondary minerals.

Gold Au

Native gold has been found with some frequency as small sheets and submillimeter grains of a maximum size of 0.7 mm, associated with native bismuth and its oxides, within the quartz vein.

Bismuth Bi

Native bismuth is very frequently included in the quartz vein, generally as monocrystalline grains (anhedral crystals) from which the exfoliation planes are observed. These grains have a size of up to 12 mm, with a white silvery color slightly pinkish and with the typical brightness of this mineral. Native bismuth usually has a halo of secondary minerals, usually oxides.

Sphalerite ZnS

Sphalerite appears with some frequency in this mine as very dark brown microcrystals, associated with groups of bismuthinite crystals, and also as groups of crystals of up to 1 mm, rhombododecahedral, in quartz geodes.

Bismuthinite Bi_2S_3

Bismuthinite is found as cleavable masses and as individualized acicular microcrystals of up to 5 mm, forming radiating clusters within small cavities inside the quartz. These crystals can appear bright and without traces of alteration, or partially or totally altered to other minerals.

Molybdenite MoS_2

Molybdenite is quite frequent as irregular, bright laminar crystals, up to 5 millimeters in size, within the massive quartz vein and rarely inside geodes, as free crystals with altered contours.

Pyrite FeS_2

Pyrite microcrystals with a cube or pyritohedron shape, usually totally oxidized, appear quite frequently in cavities inside quartz geodes. Cubic crystals with modifications of octahedron faces up to a size of 2 mm, unaltered, associated with ferberite, have been found occasionally.

Arsenopyrite FeAsS

As already indicated, arsenopyrite is a very rare mineral in this deposit, but occasionally centimetric masses and isolated crystals have been found inside the quartz. Some groups of microcrystals, with their characteristic habit, have also been found.

Fluorite CaF_2

Fluorite is occasionally found as corroded cubic crystals with a maximum size of 5 mm with irregular faces, with a very light violet color with darker patches irregularly distributed.

Gold. FOV 1.3 mm. Christian Rewitzer collection and photo.

Bismuth. FOV 3 mm. Christian Rewitzer collection and photo.

Sphalerite. FOV 0.8 mm. Christian Rewitzer collection and photo.

Bismoclite (BiO) Cl

Bismoclite seems to be a very rare species in the deposit since until now it has only been found in a single specimen. It appears as aggregates of snow white microcrystals, perimorphs of bismuthinite crystals which it replaces. The Cogolla Alta deposit is the first confirmed location of bismoclite in Spain.

Zavaritskite (BiO) F

This mineral has been found, very occasionally, as extremely small globular aggregates of white color over quartz. The EDS analysis confirms that it is a variety of calcium-rich zavaritskite. The deposit of Cogolla Alta is the first in which this mineral has been found in Spain.

Hematite Fe₂O₃

Hematite appears very occasionally as thin tabular crystals of hexagonal contour, with the characteristic black color and metallic appearance of this mineral, generally with their surface altered, over quartz crystals.

Bismoclite. Pseudomorph after bismuthinite.
FOV 1.4 mm. Carlos Utrera coll.
Christian Rewitzer photo.

Bismuthinite. Acicular crystals. FOV 5 mm.
Carlos Utrera coll. Christian Rewitzer photo.

Bismite Bi_2O_3

Bismite is quite frequent in this deposit, but it can be confused with other minerals formed by the alteration of native bismuth and bismuthinite. It appears as earthy or powdery masses of white, beige or yellow color. Also very rarely aggregates of microscopic crystals of grayish color, forming pseudomorphosis, possibly of bismuthinite, have been found. Bismite totally replaces the primary mineral, leaving an internal tubular cavity. When alteration minerals pseudomorphize bismuthinite crystals, bismite and beyerite are visually indistinguishable. Bismoclite has a more intensely white color, without the flaky texture of the other minerals, while cannonite appears as colorless needle-like microcrystals practically perpendicular to those of altered bismuthinite.

Quartz SiO_2

Quartz is the most abundant component of the mineralization, forming the veins exploited to obtain wolframite. In addition to massive veins, quartz also appears as groups of colorless crystals of a few millimeters forming the walls of multiple cavities. The crystals of the most notable secondary minerals are deposited over these quartz crystals. In some geodes filled with clay, floating colorless biterminated quartz crystals of up to 15mm have been found with very little development of the prism. Very flattened crystals have also appeared.

Bismite, pseudomorph after bismuthinite crystals. FOV 0.8 mm. C. Utrera coll. C. Rewitzer photo.

Cassiterite SnO_2

Cassiterite appears occasionally as microcrystals of very dark brown, almost black, shiny up to 3 mm.

Ferberite FeWO_4

Ferberite is the main tungsten mineral of this deposit. It appeared as masses inside quartz. It is still relatively frequent in the tailings, and centimetric sections of idiomorphic crystals can be observed. Free crystals inside quartz geodes are very rare.

Anatase. Bipyramidal crystal associated to clinocllore. FOV 1.2 mm. C. Rewitzer coll. and photo.

Anatase and brookite. FOV 0.4 mm. C. Utrera coll. C. Rewitzer photo.

Anatase TiO_2

Anatase occurs occasionally as bipyramidal crystals, with a very dark blue color, almost black, with a maximum size of 1 mm. The crystals can have a dipyramidal habit in which the acute dipyramid {101} predominates, sometimes accompanied by the prism {100}, with or without the pinacoid {001}, and also tabular, with the predominance of the latter form. In some cases, in very small crystals observed by SEM, the presence of {112} has also been observed. Anatase is mainly associated with brookite and clinocllore, and occasionally also with austinite.

Brookite TiO_2

Brookite has occasionally been found as thin tabular orange-colored crystals of submillimeter size, associated with anatase and clinocllore.

Koehlinite Bi_2MoO_6

This mineral can be found as yellow masses, with a waxy aspect and sometimes with a somewhat leafy structure, replacing masses of primary sulphides. It is possible that at least in some cases the leafy structure is due to a pseudomorphic alteration of molybdenite aggregates. We have found in the Cogolla Alta mine koehlinite with a certain content of tungsten. Although it has not been studied in sufficient detail to confirm it, it seems possible that there is a series between the koehlinite and russellite, which is isostructural with it.

Koehlinite. FOV 2 mm.

Christian Rewitzer coll. and photo.

Russellite Bi_2WO_6

Russellite is relatively frequent in this mine. It is found as small compact masses of beige or yellowish color in which russellite appears associated with koehlinite. This association is frequent between these two minerals, having been found in other deposits. In fact, in the second location where russellite was found in the world, Poona, Murchison Division, Western Australia, russellite forms with the koehlinite an aggregate in which both minerals are inseparable by mechanical means (Hodge, 1970). Russellite is also found, more rarely, as pseudomorphs after bismuthinite.

However, the most interesting specimens are those in which russellite appears as tiny whitish globular aggregates up to 0.5 mm in diameter formed by very fine scaly crystals. This type of specimens have also been found in the “Alcantarilla” mine (Rewitzer et al., 2016), next to “Cogolla Alta” mine, in the “Clara” mine, Oberwolfach, Baden-Württemberg (Germany) and in Zinwald / Cinovec, between Germany and the Czech Republic (base de datos de mindat.org). So far, russellite has been found in Spain only at this mine and in the neighboring “Alcantarilla” mine.

Russellite. Globular aggregates of scaly microcrystals FOV 0.8 mm. C.Rewitzer coll. and photo.

Molybdate MoO_3

Molybdate appears with some frequency in this locality as crusts of intense yellow color, with waxy aspect, as a product of alteration of molybdenite, directly associated with crystalline sheets of this mineral.

Smithsonite. Sub-parallel growth of microcrystals in the form of "rice grain". FOV 1.5 mm. C. Utrera coll. C. Rewitzer photo.

Smithsonite. FOV 0.4 mm. C. Utrera coll. C. Rewitzer and photo.

Smithsonite ZnCO_3

Smithsonite appears occasionally in cavities inside the quartz as aggregates of bad defined crystals, of irregular development, with elongated fusiform aspect, almost acicular, or also in the form of "rice grain", typical of this mineral. It appears as colorless or with a slightly pink tone, due in the latter case to the presence of some cobalt replacing zinc.

Kettnerite. Sub-parallel aggregate of lamellar microcrystals. FOV 0.8 mm. C. Utrera coll. C. Rewitzer photo.

Kettnerite. Sub-parallel aggregate of lamellar microcrystals. FOV 0.6 mm. C. Utrera coll. C. Rewitzer photo.

Kettnerite CaBiCO_3OF

Kettnerite is a very complex mineral, with an order-disorder structure with a quadratic net, which was first found in the “Barbora” pit in Krupka, Czech Republic (Hybler and Durovic, 2009). In this locality it appears in a peculiar form, as groups of laminar or tabular crystals of tetragonal aspect (really is orthorhombic), relatively well differentiated, with the face {001} as dominant, relatively well differentiated, or as spherules formed by these same crystals. In the other well-known deposits, such as in the “Clara” mine, in Oberwolfach (Germany), kettnerite appears in the form of spherules with a scaly outer surface to a greater or lesser degree. In the “Cogolla Alta” mine it has been found in both forms. The least common is as aggregates of differentiated laminar microcrystals, grouped in subparallel form on the {001} faces, forming roses with a rectangular or rhomboidal contour or as divergent agrupations, with a maximum size of 1 mm. More frequent are the spheres

Kettnerite. FOV 0.6 mm.
Christian Rewitzer coll. and photo.

Kettnerite. Aggregates in rosettes of lamellar crystals. C. Rewitzer coll. and photo.

of yellowish white or very light cream color, sometimes grouped together forming chains. The surface of those crystals is almost smooth or upholstered with bright laminar tiny microcrystals. Kettnerite has been found associated with austinite or smithsonite, and much more rarely coating galena microcrystals. When kettnerite appears as spherules, it is almost impossible to differentiate it from the other carbonates of bismuth, such as beyerite and bismutite without making specific analyses. The “Cogolla Alta” mine is the first deposit in Spain in which this mineral species has been found.

Kettnerite in lamellar microcrystalline spherules.
FOV 1.3 mm. C. Rewitzer coll. and photo.

Microcrystalline spheres of **kettnerite** on austinite crystals. FOV 2.1 mm. C. Rewitzer coll. and photos.

Beyerite $\text{Ca}(\text{BiO})_2(\text{CO}_3)_2$

Beyerite can be found in cavities inside the quartz as associations of spherules and rosettes formed by interpenetrating microscopic laminar crystals. With a color between white and yellow canary, sometimes the rosettes are grouped forming coraloid growths. Usually, beyerite of lighter tones is visually indistinguishable from kettnerite, but the globular aggregates of intense canary yellow color analyzed have turned out to be all beyerite, so this intense color can be considered as a visual indicator.

Beyerite. FOV 0.8 mm.
C. Rewitzer coll. and photo.

Beyerite in lamellar microcrystalline spheres. FOV 0.6 mm.
C. Utrera coll. C. Rewitzer photo.

Beyerite. Pseudomorph after bismuthinite. FOV 1.6 mm.
C. Utrera coll. C. Rewitzer photo.

Beyerite. Rose-shaped aggregates of laminar microcrystals; above, the microcrystals have a rounded contour, and below a well-defined crystal morphology.
C. Rewitzer SEM photos.

Beyerite. Spheres of lamellar microcrystals. FOV 1.3 mm.
C. Utrera coll. C. Rewitzer photo.

Beyerite. Spheres of lamellar microcrystals. FOV 0.8 mm.
C. Utrera coll. C. Rewitzer photo.

Cannonite with bismuthinite. C. Rewitzer SEM photo.

Cannonite with bismuthinite. FOV 1 mm.
C. Rewitzer coll. and photo.

Wulfenite $Pb(MoO_4)$

In the “Cogolla Alta” mine, wulfenite is relatively frequent as millimeter lenticular crystals, generally of irregular contour, although sometimes there are some crystals with a tabular development with well-defined faces. Its color varies between different shades of cream, yellow or even almost orange and grayish. In some specimens, the analyses show some tungsten content, corresponding then to the chillagite variety. In this case, the color is usually brownish. In this deposit wulfenite appears associated with secondary minerals of bismuth and molybdenum.

Wulfenite. Crystals in parallel growth. FOV 3 mm. C. Rewitzer coll. and photo.

Wulfenite. Aggregate of lamellar crystals. FOV 1.4 mm. C. Utrera coll. C. Rewitzer photo.

Scheelite $Ca(WO_4)$

Scheelite is a relatively abundant mineral in this deposit, appearing as crystals up to 15 mm in size inside geodes in quartz. It appears as milky white grains, dispersed in massive filonian quartz or as cream-colored coatings over ferberite. Scheelite crystals are dipyrmidal, sometimes with minor modifications of other faces, orange or yellowish, translucent or opaque, and often have iron oxides coatings. Scheelite has the characteristic blue fluorescence in short wave ultraviolet light.

Powellite $Ca(MoO_4)$

Powellite is very scarce in this deposit, appearing between the sheets of molybdenite as crystalline masses of up to 1 mm and as small dipyrmidal crystals of greenish-yellow color and vitreous gloss.

Rooseveltite $Bi(AsO_4)$

Rooseveltite is very scarce in this site and appears as submillimeter groups of whitish crystals associated with preisingerite and eulitin. So far, it has only been found in Spain in this mine and in the Alcantarilla mine (Rewitzer *et al.*, 2016).

Scheelite. Bypyrmidal crystal. FOV 3.4 mm. C. Utrera coll. C. Rewitzer photo.

Powellite. C. Rewitzer SEM photo.

Zincolibethenite and mixite.
C. Rewitzer SEM photo.

Zincolibethenite with acicular crystals of mixite.
FOV 2.1 mm. C. Rewitzer coll. and photo.

Zincolibethenite
 $\text{CuZn}(\text{PO}_4)(\text{OH})$

Zincolibethenite has been found as short prismatic crystals of pale bluish green color, forming generally compact divergent aggregates of a size of up to 0.5 mm. These tiny crystals are partially covered by needles of mixed-zalesiite and associated with austinite crystals rich in zinc. Zincolibethenite is very rare in Cogolla Alta and only a few specimens have appeared to date. This mineral is quite rare, and has only been found in a dozen locations around the world. In Spain, it had been found in the “Tita” mine, Golpejas (Salamanca) (Calvo, 2015). So far, Cogolla Alta is the second Spanish location for this rare mineral.

Adamite $Zn_2(AsO_4)(OH)$

In the “Cogolla Alta” mine, adamite appears with three distinctly different aspects depending on its color, colorless or with slight yellow tones more or less greenish or pink, depending on its chemical composition. The green tones are due to the presence of copper (cupriferous adamite, with Cu partially substituting Zn, which can exceed 10%), while pink is due to cobalt (cobaltiferous adamite, with Co substituting Zn up to a 5%). In the colorless crystals

the analyses show the absence of other cations other than zinc. The crystals of cobaltiferous adamite are transparent or translucent, they form aggregates in parallel growth or in the form of a sheaf, and they can reach a size of up to 4 mm, while those of the varieties without cobalt are much smaller. The cobaltiferous adamite is by far most frequent that non-cobaltiferous, and the one that forms the best and largest crystals. Morphology is sometimes very well defined, and completely finished crystals can be observed.

Cobaltiferous **adamite**. Prismatic crystals on quartz. FOV 4 mm. M. Calvo coll. J. Callen photo.

Adamite. FOV 0.6 mm. C. Utrera coll. C. Rewitzer photo.

Cobaltiferous **adamite**. FOV 2 mm. C. Utrera coll. C. Rewitzer photo.

Cobaltiferous **adamite**. FOV 1 mm. Tino Hiraldo coll. C. Rewitzer photo.

Although in some occasions they are completely embedded in the quartz, leaving only their sections visible, or have rounded faces. The habit is relatively simple in both cases, and characteristic of this mineral, with the crystals formed by {011} as the main figure, elongated in the direction of the a axis, combined with lesser faces {013} and ending with {110} (Calvo, 2015).

Cobaltiferous adamite is the most abundant mineral in this mine among all those that contain cobalt. Adamite is a relatively common mineral worldwide, but not so much the cobaltiferous variety, especially as good crystals. Specimens comparable to those of Cogolla Alta have only been found at the Cerro Minado mine in Huerca Overa, Almería (Spain) (Favreau *et al.*, 2013), in that of Kamariza, Agios Constantinos, Laurion, Greece, and in that of Vignola, Val Sugana, Trento, Italy (Boscardin *et al.*, 1978).

Cobaltiferous adamite crystals with chlorite. FOV 4 mm. C. Utrera coll. C. Rewitzer photo.

Cobaltiferous adamite. FOV 2.4 mm. C. Rewitzer coll. and photo.

Paradamite $Zn_2(AsO_4)(OH)$

In the quartz geodes of the vein of the “Cogolla Alta” mine, groupings of white to cream microcrystals have been found very occasionally. When this mineral is examined by SEM-EDS those crystals show a morphology corresponding to the triclinic system, and a chemical composition compatible with that of paradamita. Due to the limited amount of sample available, it has not been possible to perform further analysis, so its identification is considered tentative.

Arsenbrackebuschite $Pb_2Fe^{3+}(AsO_4)_2(OH)$

Brown monoclinic microcrystals have been found whose chemical composition, analyzed by EDS, corresponds to that of the arsenbrackebuschite, with a small amount of vanadium replacing arsenic.

Heyite - Calderonite $Pb_2Fe^{3+}(VO_4)_2(OH)$

Brown microcrystals have been found on quartz that have a chemical composition almost coincident with that corresponding to this species, with small amounts of arsenic. This suggests that there may be a solid solution with the arsenbrackebuschite.

Tilasite $CaMg(AsO_4)F$

Tilasite appears with some frequency in the “Cogolla Alta” mine, in the form of cream-white spherules, sometimes with a glossy clean surface, of up to 1.5 mm diameter, in quartz geodes. Sometimes, in these spherules is intergrown with austinite. Tilasite is a rare mineral that has been found, generally as relatively large crystals or as granular masses, in mineral deposits of Zn and Mn subjected to processes of metamorphism. We have not found other cases of the presence of tilasite with the morphology and in the type of deposit studied in this case. This is the first time that tilasite is identified in a Spanish locality.

Paradamite. FOV 0.4 mm. Group of microcrystals. Above: SEM photo. Below: with light. C. Rewitzer coll. and photo.

Tilasite. Radiated spherules. FOV 3 mm. C. Utrera coll. C. Rewitzer photo.

Arsenbrackebuschite. Microcrystals layer. C. Rewitzer SEM photo.

Tilasite. FOV 1 mm. C. Utrera coll.
C. Rewitzer photo.

Tilasite. FOV 1 mm. C. Rewitzer coll. and photo.

Tilasite. FOV 1.6 mm. Sectioned spheroid in which the showing the concentric internal structure. C. Utrera coll.
C. Rewitzer photo.

Tilasite. FOV 1.3 mm.
C. Rewitzer coll. and photo.

Cobaltaustinite $\text{CaCo}(\text{AsO}_4)(\text{OH})$

Cobaltaustinite has been found very rarely as microcrystals of an intense green color characteristic of this mineral, associated with cobaltlotharmeyerite, on quartz crystals. The origin of the green color is not clear. In some specimens, as in those of the type locality, Dome Rock, in Australia, it is probably due to the presence of copper, since this mineral forms a series with conicalcite (Nickel and Birch, 1988). However, in other cases, as in “Cogolla Alta”, copper is practically absent in cobaltaustinite, containing instead Zn and Ni, with approximate proportions Co/Zn/Ni 6/3/1. Specimens with a composition similar to this one, also of intense green color, have been found in vein 2 of Bou-Azzer (Favreau, 2007). Cobaltaustinite is a rare mineral, known in about a dozen localities, half of them in the district of Bou-Azzer, in Morocco. The “Cogolla Alta” mine is the first one in which this mineral is found in Spain.

Cobaltaustinite and **cobaltlotharmeyerite**. FOV 1.3 mm. C. Rewitzer coll. and photo.

Austinite. FOV 1 mm. Microcrystals in parallel growth. M. Calvo coll. J. Callen photo.

Austinite $\text{CaZn}(\text{AsO}_4)(\text{OH})$

Austinite is found as relatively well-formed crystals, with a bright yellowish, yellow-green, very pale green or cream color, translucent, sometimes with very marked color zoning, so that the internal part of the crystals is whitish and almost opaque. Austinite crystals can reach a size of up to 2 millimeters, have prismatic development, elongated in the direction of the c axis, and are formed by the combination of {110} as a dominant figure, with {101} rather minor, and sometimes accompanied by very small faces of {111}. The larger crystals can form small disordered groups. It also appears as parallel growth crystals and tiny spherules formed by divergent crystals (Calvo, 2015). Occasionally, aggregates of grass-green colored crystals have been found, belonging to the series that this mineral forms with the conicalcite, that is, with a significant copper content, but with austinite as the dominant term. Austinite is also quite frequent as radiated spheres that can reach a diameter of up to 5 mm. The inner part is usually whitish, with a very light green tone sometimes almost negligible, opaque and almost dull.

Austinite. Prismatic crystals in a vug of quartz. FOV 1.4 mm. C. Utrera coll. C. Rewitzer photo.

Austinite. Microcrystals with internal zonations.
FOV 3 mm. C. Utrera coll. C. Rewitzer photo.

Austinite. FOV 2.1 mm. Col. C. Utrera.
Foto C. Rewitzer.

Austinite. FOV 1.4 mm. Col. C. Utrera. Foto C. Rewitzer.

Austinite. FOV 4 mm. C. Rewitzer coll. and photo.

Austinite. FOV 1.6 mm. Col. C. Utrera.
Foto C. Rewitzer.

Austinite. FOV 1.8 mm. C. Rewitzer coll. and photo.

Conichalcite $\text{CaCu}(\text{AsO}_4)(\text{OH})$

Conichalcite, is very rare in this locality, appearing as globular aggregates of apple green color, up to 0.2 mm in diameter, over quartz. There is a series between conicalcita and austinita, and most of the analyses of the members of this series determined that the specimens had the term Austinite as dominant.

Descloizite $\text{PbZn}(\text{VO}_4)(\text{OH})$

Vanadium minerals are very rare in the “Cogolla Alta” mine, although some specimens of descloizite and vanadinite have been found very occasionally. Descloizite is probably the most abundant vanadium mineral, appearing as dipyramidal crystals with truncated vertices of a size of 0.3 mm of brownish-

orange color, with quite marked zonings, with the center lighter than the outside. Descloizite has some content of As, up to 5% in weight, not a single specimen in which the dominant term is arsenodescloizite has been found. It is associated with hedyphane, wulfenite and kettnerite.

Segnitite $\text{PbFe}^{3+}_3(\text{AsO}_4)_2(\text{OH},\text{H}_2\text{O})_6$

A single specimen has been found, with very small yellow crystals on quartz, whose chemical composition and morphology, examined by SEM / EDS corresponds to segnitite. Unfortunately, given the lack of other samples, it has not been possible to carry out other confirmatory analyses.

Conichalcite. FOV 2.4 mm.
C. Utrera coll. C. Rewitzer photo.

Descloizite. FOV 1.6 mm. C. Utrera coll. C. Rewitzer photo.

Segnitite. C. Rewitzer SEM photo.

Segnitite. FOV 0.9 mm. C. Rewitzer coll. and photo.

Dugganite $\text{Pb}_3\text{Zn}_3(\text{AsO}_4)_2(\text{TeO}_6)$

Dugganite was described as a new mineral species from specimens obtained at the Tombstone gold mines (Williams, 1978). In the original publication it was already indicated the fact that the color of this mineral was quite variable depending on the presence of copper in a greater or lesser proportion. In fact, almost all the specimens known to date of this mineral have green color, with different shades, with the exception of some from the Gold Chain Mine, in Mammoth, Utah, USA, which have an orange color, similar to the “Cogolla Alta” specimens. The composition of the “Cogolla Alta” dugganite is very similar to that of the type locality (Williams, 1978) with a slightly higher content

of phosphorus and a slightly lower content of tellurium. In this mine, dugganite is found as prismatic crystals with tabular development and hexagonal contour, with {001} as main figure, with {100} less developed, forming aggregates with rose shape of curved subparallel crystals, a very characteristic morphology, which makes it easy to identify. No copper is detected by SEM-EDS, but a small amount of phosphorus is detected. The crystals are white, orange or pale violet in color, up to half a millimeter in size, which is quite large for this species. It is relatively frequent, associated with cobaltoan adamite, kettnerite and other bismuth minerals. The Cogolla Alta mine is the only locality known to date in Europe where dugganite appears.

Dugganite. Aggregates in the form of rosettes produced by the sub-parallel growth of tabular crystals. C. Rewitzer SEM photos.

Dugganite. FOV 1.2 mm. C. Rewitzer coll. and photo.

Dugganite. FOV 0.8 mm. C. Rewitzer coll. and photo.

Dugganite on scheelite. Left: individual microcrystals. Right: dugganite crystals covering completely a scheelite crystal. FOV 0.8 mm. C Utrera coll. C. Rewitzer photo.

Dugganite. FOV 0.6 mm. C. Utrera coll. C. Rewitzer photo.

Dugganite with russellite. FOV 2.2 mm. C. Rewitzer coll. and photo.

Dugganite. FOV 0.6 mm. C. Utrera coll. C. Rewitzer photo.

Dugganite. FOV 0.8 mm. C. Rewitzer coll. and photo.

Fluorapatite $\text{Ca}_5(\text{PO}_4)_3\text{F}$

Fluorapatite has been found occasionally as microcrystals with a prismatic bacillary development, colorless, with hexagonal contour and with the termination formed by the combination of bipyramid and pinacoid.

Hedyphane $\text{Ca}_2\text{Pb}_3(\text{AsO}_4)_3\text{Cl}$

Hedyphane is very scarce in this deposit, having been found as hexagonal crystals formed by the combination of prism and bipyramid, very coarse, with multiple regrowths on the faces and in some cases with a hollow core, with the axis of the cavity coinciding with the prism axis. In the very few samples of hedyphane, the size of the crystals does not exceed 3 mm, and they form small groups, associated with kettnerite, wulfenite and descloizite.

Mimetite $\text{Pb}_5(\text{AsO}_4)_3\text{Cl}$

Mimetite forms a solid solution with hedyphane, and in “Cogolla Alta” there are specimens with one or other of these terms as dominant. Mimetite appears rarely, with the typical hexagonal crystals in quartz cavities, associated with austinite and adamite.

Vanadinite $\text{Pb}_5(\text{VO}_4)_3\text{Cl}$

Vanadinite has been found very occasionally, as bad-defined microcrystals, with a size of less than 100 microns, of a orange-brown to grey-brown color.

Preisingerite $\text{Bi}_3(\text{AsO}_4)_2\text{O}(\text{OH})$

Preisingerite appears as aggregates of white to pale yellow colored rhomboidal plates or very dark beige aggregates, up to 0.5 mm in size. The luster of the preisingerite is subadamantine. This mineral seems very scarce in Cogolla Alta because only very few samples have been recovered so far.

Fluorapatite. FOV 1 mm. C. Utrera coll. C. Rewitzer photo.

Hedyphane. FOV 3 mm. C. Utrera coll. C. Rewitzer photo.

Preisingerite. SEM photo C. Rewitzer.

Preisingerite. FOV 2 mm. C. Utrera coll. C. Rewitzer photo.

Atelestite $\text{Bi}_2(\text{AsO}_4)\text{O}(\text{OH})$

Atelestite occurs generally as divergent aggregates of prismatic crystals, arranged in approximately radially form. Its color is milky white or very pale bluish gray, with adamantine luster. This mineral appears associated with kettnerite and bismuthinite. It has also been found as bluish-gray tubular formations, formed by the grouping of microcrystals. Probably in this case it is the result of the direct alteration of acicular crystals of bismuthinite, to which it would pseudomorphize. Atelestite is a relatively widespread mineral in the bismuth mineralizations of Germany. However, in Spain it has been found only at the “Alcantarilla” mine (Rewitzer et al., 2106) and “Cogolla Alta”, being a very rare mineral in both cases.

Schlegelite $\text{Bi}_7(\text{AsO}_4)_3(\text{MoO}_4)_2\text{O}_4$

Schlegelite is an extraordinarily rare mineral, to the extent that until now it was only known in a single specimen, the type specimen, discovered in the tailings of the well “Pucher”, in the mining district of Schneeberg (Saxony), Germany (Krause et al., 2006). The “Cogolla Alta” mine is the second locality in which it is found in the world, and also here it is very rare, having only appeared so far in one specimen.

It is found as groupings of a size of 0.4 mm formed by divergent acicular microcrystals of grayish yellow color. Given the scarcity of the sample, the mineral has been identified only by SEM / EDS, a technique that allows us to deduce a composition that fits very well with that of schlegelite. In this locality, schlegelite is associated with native bismuth, bismite, molybdenite and molybdate.

Schlegelite. C. Rewitzer SEM photo.

Schlegelite. FOV 0.6 mm. C. Rewitzer coll. and photo.

Atelestite. FOV 0.7 mm.
C. Utrera coll. C. Rewitzer photo.

Atelestite. C. Rewitzer SEM photo.

Mansfieldita. C. Rewitzer SEM photo.

Scorodite-mansfieldite solid solution is relatively scarce in the “Cogolla Alta” mine, much less frequent than in the “Alcantarilla” mine, reflecting the lower presence of arsenopyrite among primary minerals. It appears as globular aggregates of pseudo-octahedral microcrystals with a whitish gray color. Although in most of the “Cogolla Alta” specimens analyzed the dominant term is scorodite, some have been found in which the predominant term is mansfieldite. The appearance is the same, and both species are visually indistinguishable.

Scorodite. FOV 1.3 mm.
C. Utrera coll. C. Rewitzer photo.

Mansfieldite. FOV 1 mm. C. Rewitzer coll. and photo.

Erythrite $\text{Co}_3(\text{AsO}_4)_2 \cdot 8\text{H}_2\text{O}$

As already indicated, one of the characteristics that differentiate the veins exploited in the “Alcantarilla” and “Cogolla Alta” claims is the existence of cobalt minerals in the latter. Although erythrite is the most common secondary cobalt mineral, it is very rare in Cogolla Alta. It appears forming the characteristic divergent groups of millimetric purple tabular crystals.

Erythrite. FOV 1.4 mm. C. Utrera coll. C. Rewitzer photo.

Talmessite. C. Rewitzer SEM photo.

Talmessite $\text{Ca}_2\text{Mg}(\text{AsO}_4)_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$

In the “Cogolla Alta” mine, talmessite has been identified only by EDS, in a single specimen, as aggregates of white crystals forming urchins up to 1 mm in diameter. It is associated with adamita and austinite.

Gaitite $\text{Ca}_2\text{Zn}(\text{AsO}_4)_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$

Gaitite is a very rare mineral, whose presence has been indicated so far in very few locations, being also scarce in all of them. In the “Cogolla Alta” mine it is a rare mineral, and has been found associated with austinite forming divergent aggregates of up to 2 mm of pale gray-green laminar crystals, and also as thin white coatings on the austinite crystals themselves.

Gaitite. FOV 2 mm. C. Utrera coll. C. Rewitzer photo.

Gaitite. FOV 0.6 mm. C. Utrera coll. C. Rewitzer photo.

Cobaltlotharmeyerite

This mineral has occasionally been found as aggregates of extremely small, tabular crystals, with $\{101\}$ as the dominant figure, slightly rounded and spatula-like, of an orange-brown color. It appears associated with cobaltaustinite, in quartz cavities.

Cobaltlotharmeyerite was described as a new mineral species from specimens found in the mining area of "Am Roten Berg", in Schneeberg, Germany, having also been found in the tailings of the "Pucher" and "Rappold" mines (Krause et al., 1999). On a global scale, this mineral has only been found in a few mines in the German district of Schneeberg and in the Moroccan district of Bou-Azer (Hazen et al, 2017), always with the same appearance as indicated here. In the "Cogolla Alta" mine, which is the first cobaltlotharmeyerite locality for Spain, it appears associated with cobaltaustinite, an association that is also found in the Bou-Azer field.

Cobaltlotharmeyerite. Divergent aggregates of microcrystals on quartz. FOV 1.1 mm. C. Rewitzer coll. and photo.

Tooeleite $\text{Fe}^{3+}_6(\text{As}^{3+}\text{O}_3)_4(\text{SO}_4)(\text{OH})_4 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$

Although tooeleite has been found occasionally in the "Cogolla Alta" mine, as orange spherules with radiated internal structure, it is much rarer than in the neighboring "Alcantarilla" mine. It appears associated with scorodite.

Arsenosiderite $\text{Ca}_2\text{Fe}^{3+}_3(\text{AsO}_4)_3\text{O}_2 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$

Arsenosiderite has been found very occasionally as very thin felted layers, brown in color and with the characteristic brightness of this mineral.

Cobaltlotharmeyerite. Tabular microcrystal aggregates on quartz. FOV 1.1 mm. C. Rewitzer coll. and photo.

Tooeleite. Microcrystal on quartz. FOV 0.6 mm. C. Utrera coll. C. Rewitzer photo.

Mixite $\text{BiCu}_6(\text{AsO}_4)_3(\text{OH})_6 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$

Mixite appears in the “Cogolla Alta” mine as small plumes formed by the divergent grouping of acicular microcrystals, or as sub-parallel aggregates formed by this same type of crystals. Mixite has a bluish light green color, and is usually associated with zincolibethenite.

Zalesiite $\text{CaCu}_6(\text{AsO}_4)_2(\text{AsO}_3\text{OH})(\text{OH})_6 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$

Zalesiite, a mineral from the same group as mixite, is also present in this deposit as groups of acicular microcrystals of the same color and appearance as those of mixite, being therefore visually indistinguishable.

Mixite. Aggregate of acicular microcrystals on a quartz crystal. FOV 2 mm. C. Utrera coll. C. Rewitzer photo.

Bertrandite. Tabular microcrystals. C. Rewitzer SEM photo.

The analysis of the chemical composition by EDS, shows an intermediate composition between mixite and zalesiite. This allows to suspect the probable existence of a series among them.

Eulytine $\text{Bi}_4(\text{SiO}_4)_3$

Extremely small crystals (less than 10 microns) of eulytine have been found. Eulytine appears with an intense yellow color, with the cone shape that crystals of this mineral sometimes have, a cone that is actually a very deformed tetrahedron (or trisraedron) with rounded faces. These crystals appear associated with preisingerite and rooseveltite.

Bertrandite $\text{Be}_4(\text{Si}_2\text{O}_7)(\text{OH})_2$

Beryllium minerals seem to be extraordinarily rare in this deposit. A single specimen has been found in which bertrandite appears as groups of tabular, elongated, colorless and transparent crystals of up to 0.25 mm.

Eulytine. Parallel association of microcrystals (above) and microcrystals associated with others of preisingerite (below). C. Rewitzer SEM photo.

Muscovite $KAl_2(AlSi_3O_{10})(OH)_2$

Muscovite is found as groupings of thin or laminar, transparent or translucent tabular crystals with a hexagonal contour, up to 5 mm in size. The sericite variety can also be found, with a yellowish white color, upholstering geodes in quartz associated with feldspars.

Clinocllore $Mg_5Al(AlSi_3O_{10})(OH)_8$

Chamosite $(Fe^{2+}, Mg, Al, Fe^{3+})_6(Si_3O_{10})(OH)_8$

Chlorite, both with a composition in which clinocllore is the dominant term and with a composition in which the chamosite dominates, is quite frequently found inside the quartz geodes as vermiform aggregates of microcrystals sub-parallel oriented, millimeter-sized. Color is very dark olive green, almost black.

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Other minerals

Galena is an extraordinarily scarce mineral in this deposit, and has only been detected in a single specimen among all the studied. However, it is likely that, along with bismuth sulfosalts that have not been identified, is the carrier of the lead found in the secondary minerals. Small crystals of marcasite, altered in part, have been found very occasionally filling cracks in the quartz. Goethite has been found with some frequency, pseudomorphizing pyrite crystals, and also as spherical aggregates of brown microcrystals on the quartz geodes. Calcite is very rare, although occasionally it has found partially filling quartz geodes, as transparent and colorless spiky masses that sometimes show faces of scalenohedrons. Siderite is also very rare; some rhombohedral crystals partially altered to iron oxides and hydroxides have been found. Dickite has been found very occasionally as cream-colored spheres with greasy luster, smaller than a millimeter, in geodes in quartz. Feldspar (assignable to the variety adularia) appears in pointed rhombohedral crystals pink or cream white, up to 5 mm, in the fractures and cavities in the quartz veins in contact with the encapsulating granite rock.

In the “Cogolla Alta” mine there are also other minerals that, due to their small size and to the difficulty in carrying out complementary analyzes by SEM / EDS have not been correctly identified. One of the analyzed anatase specimens has a high zirconium content, so the existence of srilankite could be suspected in this locality. There are also doubts about the presence of anglesite, ilmenite, kaatialite and β -roselite. Given the characteristics of the deposit, it is possible that in the future other minerals not described in this article may appear.

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